

SHORT COMMUNICATIONS

Vanadium (V) Complexes with *N*-benzoylphenylhydroxylamine and its Analogues

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In course of the investigation of the analytical behaviour of the aromatic hydroxylamines with vanadium¹ besides the observation that with the change in the bulkiness of the group in the para-position in the order $\text{CH}_3 \rightarrow \text{Cl} \rightarrow \text{H}$, there is an orderly decrease in selectivity, another interesting finding which is the subject matter of the note is that the colour intensities of the complexes formed in hydrochloric acid medium are greatly reduced and even changed to different hues on the addition of even traces of alcohol. That vanadium forms two types of complexes is apparent since on the addition of more alcohol to the chloroform extracts of the vanadium complexes, the absorption maxima of the extracts changed from 510/530 μ to 440 μ which is the maximum absorption region of the complexes formed at pH 4.8 to 6.0. In solutions, however, the complexes bear a ratio 1 : 2 (metal:reagent).

Attempts have, therefore, been made for the isolation and study of the properties of these complexes, formed in strong hydrochloric acid solution and at a higher pH. Both these in the solid state have been found to be diamagnetic as expected and are of compositions VOL_2Cl and $\text{V}_2\text{O}_3\text{L}_4$, respectively, where LH=aromatic hydroxylamine. The compounds of the first type impart violet colour to solutions in acetone, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride and benzene, while in alcohol or pyridine the colour is orange. Those of the second type are deep brown in colour and are soluble in all the solvents mentioned above giving orange colour to the solutions. However, on the addition of conc. hydrochloric acid to the alcoholic solution of both the complexes, the colour changes from orange to violet.

EXPERIMENTAL

Reagents:—These aromatic hydroxylamines, such as *N*-benzoylphenyl-, *N*-benzoyl-*p*-chlorophenyl-, *N*-benzoyl-*o*-tolyl- and *N*-benzoyl-*p*-tolylhydroxylamines were prepared according to the methods described¹⁻⁴.

Preparation of the complexes:

VOL_2Cl : 0.005 mole of NH_4VO_3 was dissolved by boiling in 30 ml water containing one or two drops of strong ammonia solution and to this 40 ml of conc. hydrochloric acid was added. This was then mixed with 0.01 mole of the reagent solution in 140 ml of

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2. A. K. Majumdar and A. K. Mukherjee, *Anal. Chim. Acta.*, 1958, **19**, 23.
3. A. K. Majumdar and B. K. Pal, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **42**, 43.
4. B. K. Pal, Ph. D. Thesis, Jadavpur University, 1964.

acetone. On keeping this in the cold for 4–6 hr, the violet complex separated. This was filtered, washed thoroughly with water and dried in the air.

$V_2O_3L_4$: 0.005 mole of NH_4VO_3 were dissolved in 30 ml water with the addition of one or two drops of strong ammonia solution as stated above. This was first mixed with 0.01 mole of the reagent solution in 60 ml of alcohol and then with a solution containing 0.01 mole of NaOH. After digesting on a steam-bath for a few minutes, this was allowed to cool in an ice-bath and then diluted with water. The complex separated was filtered, washed with water and dried in a vacuum desiccator. These complexes are somewhat hygroscopic. The analytical data are given in Table I.

TABLE I

Complexes	Metal (per cent)		Nitrogen (per cent)		Chlorine (per cent)	
	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
1. N-Benzoyl-phenyl hydroxylamine VO (C ₁₃ H ₁₀ O ₂ N) ₂ Cl V ₂ O ₃ (C ₁₃ H ₁₀ O ₂ N) ₄	9.57	9.68	5.23	5.32	6.71	6.74
2. N-Benzoyl- <i>o</i> -tolylhydroxylamine VO (C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₂ N) ₂ Cl V ₂ O ₃ (C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₂ N) ₄	9.08	9.19	5.11	5.05	6.28	6.40
3. N-Benzoyl- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl hydroxylamine VO (C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ NCl) ₂ Cl V ₂ O ₃ (C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ NCl) ₄	8.62	8.56	4.77	4.70	18.73	18.99
4. N-Benzoyl- <i>p</i> -tolylhydroxylamine VO (C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₂ N) ₂ Cl V ₂ O ₃ (C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₂ N) ₄	9.16	9.19	4.98	5.05	6.34	6.40
	9.58	9.66	5.28	5.31	—	—

Magnetic susceptibility measurements:—Magnetic measurements of solids were made by the Gouy method with mercury tetrathiocyanato cobaltate as standard.

The complexes may be given structural representation as

